

Lorentz Boosted Temperature and Index of Refraction

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In the literature (1), different prescriptions are given for the change in temperature under a Lorentz boost. The Landsberg approach suggests that temperature should be evaluated in a rest frame, but other prescriptions suggest that $T' = Tg(v)$ or $T' = T/g(v)$, where $g(v) = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and other prescriptions may exist.

Here, we note that the index of refraction changes with temperature, i.e. light moves faster in a hot material (2), but this behaviour may have nothing to do with Lorentz boosts, but is rather a property of the material. An issue that seems to arise with T' differing from T is that one may calculate the index of refraction as seen from a frame watching the material move and there is no dependence of this calculation on temperature. We suggest that this supports the Landsberg view.

Prescriptions for Lorentz Boosted Temperatures

In the literature (1), there exist different prescriptions for the change in temperature under a Lorentz boost of a system. The Planck prescription is:

$$T' = T/g(v), \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((1))$$

while the Ott prescription is: $T' = Tg(v)$ ((2))

Other prescriptions are also possible, it seems.

The Landsberg prescription is that one measure T (temperature) in the rest frame. This idea is supported in (2) in which $S(\mathbf{p}, E) \cdot (\mathbf{p}, E)$, i.e. entropy S does not depend on E , but on the dot product of the 4-vector (\mathbf{p}, E) which yields energy in the rest frame.

Temperature Dependence of the Index of Refraction

The index of refraction is dependent on temperature. This dependence may be measured experimentally and probably has nothing to do with boost prescriptions ((1)), ((2)) or other similar prescriptions. The hotter the medium, the faster the speed of light. (3).

Lorentz Boosted Index of Refraction

The Lorentz boosted index of refraction may be calculated without any consideration of temperature and one may find that n' is not the same as n . Given that n' is different, one might argue that n' is like n (rest n) at a different temperature, but this temperature dependence may not be simple and may depend on the material. In particular, it is noted in (3) that the index of refraction changes with temperature by .00045 per C degree for a wide range of materials i.e. a value n at T_1 would be $n - .00045$ at $T_1 + 1$. The statement that this rule holds for a wide range

of materials means that it does not hold for all. If a Lorentz boost changes temperature in a systematic way and one has a non-temperature related change for a boosted n , then it seems that there should be a rule for all materials if a material indeed has a hotter temperature when moving.

Change in Index of Refraction Under a Lorentz Boost

In (4), the change in the index of refraction under a Lorentz boost is given for an angle "a" between the light momentum vector and the medium velocity. Here we consider the simpler case of $a=0$, i.e. the light momentum is in the x direction as is v , the boost velocity. We try to find n' in two ways.

Method 1 - (p,E) vector transformation

$$\begin{aligned} |p'| &= |g -gv| |p| \quad ((3)) \\ |e'| &= |-gv \ g| |e| \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{For } e = p \ c/n, \quad p'/e' = (-v/c+n) / (1-(v/c)n) \quad ((4))$$

This matches the value from (4).

Method 2 Position-time

In the rest frame, the observer sees light enter the medium at (x_1,t_1) and reach the end at (x_2,t_2) where $(x_2-x_1) = (c/n) (t_2-t_1)$.

Using the matrix in ((3)) (Lorentz boost):

$$X_2' - x_1' = g((x_2-x_1) -vg(t_2-t_1)) = g(x_2-x_1) [1- (v/c) n]$$

$$T_2' - t_1' = g(t_2-t_1) - gv(x_2-x_1) = g(x_2-x_1)(n-v/c)$$

$$\text{Thus: } (x_2' - x_1' = (c/n') (t_2' - t_1')) \text{ so } n' = (n-v/c) / (1-nv/c) \quad ((5))$$

As a result, the boosted light speed is different than what is seen in the rest frame, but no temperature changes under a boost considerations come into play. It is known, however, that n is a function of temperature as is n' . If n is measured at T_1 , then one might try to find a T_2 mapping to n' , but this is probably is material dependent unlike the non-material dependent statements ((1)) and ((2)) which only depend on a Lorentz boost. The calculations in (4), and above do not seem to make use of temperature issues at all.

We suggest that this may indicate that the Landsberg idea that one measure T (temperature) in the rest frame is the one to use.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that different prescriptions suggest that temperature changes in different ways under a Lorentz boost, e.g. $T' = T/g(v)$ or $T' = Tg(v)$ where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, to name two. The Landsberg approach suggests that one measure T in a rest frame.

We note that experimentally the index of refraction depends on temperature and this dependence may be material dependent according to statements in (4). One may, however, show how the index of refraction changes under a Lorentz boost without using any temperature change related ideas. If the temperature of a boosted medium is changed, this should affect the index of refraction, but only boost consideration change its value in calculations. Temperature boost prescriptions for changing T are systematic, but the effect on index of refraction differs for differing materials. Overall, one may compute n' without any notion of temperature. We suggest that this may lend support to the Landsberg notion that T should be measured in a rest frame.

References

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